

INFLUENCE OF ATTITUDE TOWARD CLINICAL SUPERVISION ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CLINICAL SUPERVISION AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE

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Influence of Attitude Toward Clinical Supervision on the Implementation of the Clinical Supervision and Teaching Performance

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to determine the influence of attitude toward clinical supervision on the level of implementation of the clinical supervision and teaching performance. This quantitative study employed a descriptive-correlational design to present static depictions and establish relationships between variables, while utilizing reflective thematic analysis to explore challenges in clinical supervision from teachers' perspectives. Stratified random sampling was used to select the 141 teacher-respondents calculated through raosoft online sample size calculator. Data were gathered through survey questionnaire. Results revealed that teachers consistently exhibited a positive attitude toward clinical supervision viewing it as a supportive mechanism for professional growth. In terms of clinical supervision, findings indicated a consistently high level of implementation across three stages; pre observation, actual observation and post-observation. Rating sheets of the teachers reflected outstanding performance by teachers across various indicators. Analysis of teachers' attitudes toward clinical supervision based on their profiles showed only significant differences in terms of position. Analysis of teachers' performance showed no significant differences based on school assignment, educational attainment, length of service or teacher positions. Findings revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' attitudes toward clinical supervision and teachers' teaching performance. The simple regression analysis indicated a significant influence of teachers' attitude on the level of clinical supervision implementation as well as between teachers' attitude and teachers' performance. In order to maximize the role that clinical supervision may play in promoting educational excellence, the study emphasizes the importance of positive attitudes and the successful implementation of clinical supervision in nurturing teachers' professional development and helping them overcome challenges. Promote continual improvement in education through training, funding, and collaboration, while advocating for leadership support and targeted training in clinical supervision.

Keywords: *clinical supervision, classroom observations, teachers' attitude, teachers' performance, level of implementation*

Introduction

Clinical supervision, as a method of overseeing teaching practices, is primarily centered on enhancing the educational process, as stressed by Nurcholiq (2017). Consequently, it plays a significant role in evaluating teachers' performance. This form of supervision aims to identify areas of weakness in teachers' execution of the educational process, which ultimately impacts their overall performance, as highlighted by Andani et al. (2017). It is important to note that clinical supervision differs from other types of supervision since it is carried out usually in three stages; pre-observation conference, observation and post-observation conference (Bencherab & Maskari, 2021).

The prevailing perception of supervision often portrays it as a process primarily focused on identifying faults and shortcomings. Many teachers commonly perceive supervision as being geared more towards evaluation for assessment purposes, rather than providing constructive support and opportunities for professional growth and the improvement of teaching and learning (Zepeda, 2017).

Clinical supervision is done through classroom observations. Classroom observation has been made obligatory within the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers-Results-Based Performance Management System (PPST-RPMS). Furthermore, it has been enhanced to be more impartial and uniform in its application. The Department of Education (DepEd) has not explicitly issued a directive or memorandum mandating the use of clinical supervision in instructional supervision. However, the RPMS Manual underscores the importance of adhering to all steps and protocols during classroom observations, with these processes encompassing pre-observation, actual observation, and post-observation. Notably, these key features closely align with the principles of clinical supervision. Consequently, it can be inferred that DepEd is incorporating clinical supervision as a means to enhance the quality of education.

Furthermore, DepEd Memorandum No. 008, issued in 2023, places significant emphasis on the scheduling of classroom observations for performance evaluation. It stipulates that all such observations must be prearranged, and the teacher being assessed should be notified of the schedule at least three working days prior to the classroom observation. This is supported with the practice in the division where the researcher belong which instructed school heads to submit an Instructional Supervisory Plan (ISP) every least week of the month.

Several studies explored clinical supervision's impact on teachers' attitudes and performance. Chaula's (2023) research on school administrators' clinical supervision practices revealed a positive link with teachers' emotions. This aligns with prior work by Strieker et al. (2016) and Diez et al. (2020), suggesting that positive attitudes toward teaching and learning supervision led to favorable professional emotions and effective teaching. Additionally, Kaur's (2018) study showed that ongoing discussions between

administrators and teachers improved novice teachers' professional emotions. However, most studies were done in foreign countries and from the perspective of the school head. A local study on the influence of clinical supervision was conducted in Davao del Sur by Bello et al. (2020), but it does not include teachers' attitude toward clinical supervision and its level of implementation.

In the division where the researcher works, an unnumbered regional memorandum was released last September 2022, encouraging school heads to conduct 12 class observations monthly regardless of the school size and population putting teachers in a small school to be observed once or twice a month. On the other hand, teachers who are in big schools will be observed only once in two or three months. Hence, this study is undertaken to investigate the influence of teachers' attitude toward clinical supervision on the level of implementation of clinical supervision and teaching performance.

Research Questions

This paper aimed to determine the influence of teachers' attitude toward clinical supervision to the level of implementation of clinical supervision and teaching performance of teachers during the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. school assignment;
 - 1.2. educational attainment;
 - 1.3. length of service; and
 - 1.4. position?
2. What is the level of teachers' attitude toward Clinical Supervision?
3. What is the level of implementation of clinical supervision in terms of the following processes:
 - 3.1. pre-observation;
 - 3.2. actual observation; and
 - 3.3. post observation?
4. What is the teachers' teaching performance during the last quarter of SY:2022-2023?
5. Is there a significant difference in teachers' attitude towards clinical supervision when grouped according to profile?
6. Is there a significant difference in teachers' teaching performance when grouped according to profile?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' attitude towards clinical supervision and the teachers' teaching performance?
8. Is there a significant influence of teachers' attitude toward clinical supervision on the level of implementation of clinical supervision?
9. Is there a significant influence of teachers' attitude toward clinical supervision on the teacher's teaching performance?
10. What are the challenges and issues in the implementation of clinical supervision?

Methodology

This study is quantitative in nature and utilized the descriptive-correlational design. This research was conducted in one of the city divisions in region 10. This division has 14 elementary schools, 1 integrated school and 8 secondary schools. For the purpose of selecting the respondents who took part in the study, a stratified random sample design was used. Based on the Raosoft online sample size calculator, it is recommended that a minimum of 141 participants be selected for this study. These 141 participants will consist of teachers from fifteen elementary schools within one of the 14 divisions in region 10, specifically those classified as Teacher 1 to 3.

This study utilized a survey questionnaire as the main instrument to answer the ten research questions. The questionnaire has five parts that gather the necessary data for the study. To ensure face validity of the research instrument, the researcher followed the six steps of response process validation (Yusof, 2019). To guarantee that the panel of raters has a clear expectation and comprehension of the assignment, the first step was preparing response process validation form also known as face validation. The second step was selecting a panel of raters. To review and critique the questionnaire and based on the target user of the tool and in this study, teachers. The third step was conducting response process validation. In this study, it was conducted online with ten raters. The fourth step was reviewing items for clarity and comprehension. The fifth step is providing score for each item based on the clarity and comprehensibility rating scale which is 1 to 4. The last step was calculating the Face Validity Index (FVI) using the formula based on Ozair et al. (2017). Prior to the calculation of FVI, the clarity and comprehension rating must be recoded as 1 (the scale of 3 or 4) or 0 (the scale of 1 or 2). If the indices meet the satisfactory level, then it can be concluded that the instrument is valid.

To ensure content validity of the research instrument, the researcher followed the six steps of content validation procedure (Yusoff, 2019). The first step of content validation was to prepare the content validation form to ensure the review panel of experts have clear expectation and understanding about the task. The second step was selecting a review panel of experts. Third was conducting content validation in an online basis for convenience and practicability. The fourth step was reviewing domain and items. Providing score on each item was the fifth step. The last step was calculating CVI following the formula cited by Yusoff (2019). Prior to the calculation of CVI, the relevance rating must be recoded as 1 (relevance scale of 3 or 4) or 0 (relevance scale of 1 or 2).

The result of the reliability coefficient of 0.919 for attitude of teachers, 0.957 for level of implementation of clinical supervision, and 0.640 for teaching performance indicated that the instrument is reliable. Frequency and percentage, mean, and standard deviation, Anova, Pearson r , simple linear regression and multiple regression were used for statistical treatment. In addition, reflective thematic analysis was utilized to determine the challenges and issues of clinical supervision based on the perspective of teachers. Reflective analysis was conducted by coding the teachers' responses in the questions given. The process involved identifying key phrases and patterns which were labeled with specific codes. Grouping the codes revealed broader themes and common challenges and issues in clinical supervision.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered, its analysis, interpretation, and discussion.

Respondents' Profile

Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents' profile in terms of school assignment, educational attainment, length of years in service, and position.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents Profile*

<i>School Assignment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Small	28	19.9
Medium	70	49.6
Big	43	30.5
Total	141	100.0
<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Bachelor's Degree	52	36.9
Master's Units	69	48.9
Master's Degree	15	10.6
Doctoral Units	5	3.5
Doctor's Degree	0	0.0
Total	141	100.0
<i>Length of Years in Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
0-5	36	25.5
6-10	43	30.5
11-15	28	19.9
16-20	14	9.9
21-above	20	14.2
Total	141	100.0
<i>Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Teacher I	81	57.4
Teacher II	27	19.1
Teacher III	33	23.4
Total	141	100.0

This comprehensive breakdown offers insights into the diverse backgrounds and experiences of the respondents. It can be seen in the table that the respondents were distributed across all type of schools. The highest number of respondents belonged to medium size schools with 70 respondents or 49.6% and the lowest number of respondents belonged to small size schools. In terms of educational attainment, the highest numbers of respondents earned master's unit in their graduate studies with 69 teachers or 48.9%. On the other hand, only five of the respondents or 3.5% earned doctoral units and no one or 0% attained a doctoral degree. When it comes to length of service, the largest proportion of participants, constituting 30.5%, reported having served in their respective positions for 6-10 years. The next significant group, at 25.5%, comprised individuals with 0-5 years of service. In addition, majority of the participants, comprising 57.4%, held the position of Teacher I, indicating a substantial presence within this category. Teacher II accounted for 19.1% of the respondents, while Teacher III constituted 23.4% of the sample.

Teachers' Attitude Towards Clinical Supervision

The data in Table 2 revealed a consistently positive attitude among teachers toward clinical supervision as evidenced by high mean scores across various indicators.

Given this result, it implied that teachers see clinical supervision as a supportive mechanism for their professional growth and improvement. Teachers view clinical supervision as beneficial for teaching effectiveness, addressing aspects like lesson planning, student engagement, and classroom management. Collaborative planning between teachers and supervisors is crucial, as clinical supervision provides guidance, constructive criticism, and feedback to improve instructional methods and encourage critical thinking (Ghavifekr et al., 2019).

Mardhiah and Rabiatul (2016) found that supportive supervision enhances teaching strategies and student participation. However, some

teachers feel uneasy about repeated observations, citing pressures like heavy workloads, self-awareness of weaknesses, and discomfort during observations. Despite these challenges, positive attitudes towards clinical supervision indicate its potential for professional development. Encouraging open communication, offering constructive feedback, and emphasizing supervision's importance can create a supportive environment for educators (Quezada et al., 2020). Graham et al. (2020) further suggest that an open-minded attitude helps teachers accept observations as opportunities for improvement, benefiting both teachers and learners.

Table 2. Mean Distribution on the Level of Teachers' Attitude Toward Clinical Supervision

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
I feel happy as this is an opportunity for me to be given technical assistance to help me improve the way I teach.	3.67	.47	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
I usually expect their feedback that will allow me to improve the way I deliver my lesson.	3.66	.48	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
I welcome them as I consider this as part of their job.	3.68	.47	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
I consider this as an opportunity to improve my teaching skills.	3.72	.47	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
I feel good for the chance to consult regarding the way I teach.	3.69	.46	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
I get excited to hear their honest feedback about my way of teaching.	3.65	.49	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
I expect very clear and objective feedback in the way I teach.	3.67	.47	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
I think that it is a good opportunity for me to identify my strengths and weaknesses.	3.70	.46	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
I am open to receiving constructive feedback and view it as a valuable part of the clinical supervision process.	3.72	.46	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
I am fine if I will be observed again.	3.53	.59	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
Total Measure	3.67	.43	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive

Note: 3.26-4.00, Strongly Agree/Highly Positive; 2.51-3.25, Agree/ Positive; 1.76-2.50, Disagree/Negative; 1.00-1.75, Strongly Disagree/ Highly Negative

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Mardhiah and Rabiatul (2016) found that supportive supervision enhances teaching strategies and student participation. However, some teachers feel uneasy about repeated observations, citing pressures like heavy workloads, self-awareness of weaknesses, and discomfort during observations. Despite these challenges, positive attitudes towards clinical supervision indicate its potential for professional development. Encouraging open communication, offering constructive feedback, and emphasizing supervision's importance can create a supportive environment for educators (Quezada et al., 2020). Graham et al. (2020) further suggest that an open-minded attitude helps teachers accept observations as opportunities for improvement, benefiting both teachers and learners.

Implementation of Clinical Supervision

Table 3 presents the level of implementation of clinical supervision across the pre-observation, actual observation, and post-observation phases. The mean scores consistently reflect a highly implemented and effective clinical supervision process.

Table 3. Consolidated Findings of the Level of Implementation of Clinical Supervision

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Pre-Observation	3.59	.43	Strongly Agree	Highly Implemented
Actual Observation	3.59	.45	Strongly Agree	Highly Implemented
Post-Observation	3.63	.45	Strongly Agree	Highly Implemented
Total Measure	3.61	.43	Strongly Agree	Highly Implemented

Note: 3.26-4.00, Strongly Agree/Highly Positive; 2.51-3.25, Agree/ Positive; 1.76-2.50, Disagree/Negative; 1.00-1.75, Strongly Disagree/ Highly Negative

The data indicated that the Post Observation stage is rated highest with a mean score of 3.63 (SD=0.45), described as strongly agreed upon and highly implemented. This suggested that teachers find the feedback on their strengths and weaknesses during this stage crucial for their professional growth and effective classroom management. Graham et al. (2020) noted that receiving feedback, whether positive or negative, is essential for professional development. Both the Actual Observation and Pre-Observation stages share a mean score of 3.59, also described as strongly agreed upon and highly implemented, indicating that teachers find these stages challenging. During actual observations, teachers are conscious of meeting observable indicators, while in pre-observations, they must defend and revise their lesson plans.

Effective professional development involves collaborative lesson study groups and the use of observation notes for objective evaluation and feedback, essential for continuous improvement (Coenders & Verhoef, 2019). Ongoing training for school heads enhances their observational skills, enabling them to provide constructive feedback and stay updated on teaching practices, which supports new teachers' success. Personalized observation notes help administrators identify areas for improvement and offer tailored resources or

mentorship (LaDonna et al., 2017).

Teachers' Teaching Performance

Table 4 presents the distribution of teachers' performance during the last quarter's clinical. In assessing teachers' performance within the Department of Education (DepEd), a comprehensive evaluation tool is utilized known as the classroom observation rating sheet. This sheet encompasses nine distinct indicators or statements that are observable within the classroom setting. These indicators have been carefully aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), ensuring that they reflect the key competencies and qualities expected of educators. It's worth noting that out of the seven domains delineated in the PPST, only five are incorporated into the rating sheet. This selection is deliberate, as it focuses solely on those domains that lend themselves to direct observation within the classroom environment, omitting the two domains which are not classroom observable indicators.

The highest-rated indicator was "Applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas," with a mean score of 4.70 (SD=0.49), described as "Integrating" and interpreted as "Outstanding."

Table 4. Mean Distribution of Teachers' Performance During the Last Quarter's Clinical Supervision for SY:2022-2023

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	4.70	.49	Outstanding	Integrating
2. Used a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.	4.62	.50	Outstanding	Integrating
3. Applied a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	4.50	.63	Outstanding	Integrating
4. Managed classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments.	4.60	.55	Outstanding	Integrating
5. Managed learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.	4.62	.53	Outstanding	Integrating
6. Used differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences.	4.56	.60	Outstanding	Integrating
7. Planned, managed and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and teaching contexts.	4.63	.50	Outstanding	Integrating
8. Selected, developed, organized and use appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.	4.60	.55	Outstanding	Integrating
9. Designed, selected, organized and used diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	4.69	.48	Outstanding	Integrating
Total Measure	4.61	.39	Outstanding	Integrating

Note: 4.50-5.00, Outstanding/Integrating; 3.50-4.49, Very Satisfactory/Consolidating; 2.50-3.49, Satisfactory/Applying; 1.50-2.49, Unsatisfactory/Developing; 1.00-1.49, Poor/Organizing

This suggested that teachers excel in integrating concepts from various subjects, which helps students see the interconnectedness of their learning. Elementary teachers, trained to teach all subjects, benefit from this approach, which is reinforced by School-Based Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions aimed at improving teaching effectiveness and collaboration (DepEd Order 35, s.2016).

The lowest-rated indicator is "Applied a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking," with a mean score of 4.50 (SD=0.63), also rated "Outstanding" but indicating a need for improvement in fostering higher-order thinking skills (HOTS). Developing these skills is crucial for students' holistic development and real-life problem-solving. Teachers are encouraged to emphasize activities that promote critical thinking (Joseph, 2019), which involves helping students connect learning to real-life situations and develop strong, reasoned arguments.

Difference in Teachers' Attitude Toward Clinical Supervision when Grouped According to Profile

Table 5 presents the analysis of differences in teachers' attitudes towards clinical supervision based on their profiles. The F-values and p-values from the One-way ANOVA test are provided to assess the significance of variations.

Table 5 analyzes differences in teachers' attitudes towards clinical supervision based on their profiles, using F-values and p-values from a One-way ANOVA test. No significant differences were found based on school assignment (F=0.886, p=0.415), educational attainment (F=0.760, p=0.519), or years in service (F=1.487, p=0.209). However, significant differences were observed based on teachers' positions (F=4.319, p=0.015). The post-hoc Duncan test revealed that Teacher I (Mean=3.75, SD=0.40) has a significantly more positive attitude towards clinical supervision than Teacher III (Mean=3.49, SD=0.47), with Teacher II (Mean=3.65, SD=0.43) in between.

This suggests the need for targeted interventions and support tailored to teachers' positions to enhance their engagement with clinical supervision. Strategies to improve Teacher III's satisfaction and ongoing support across all positions can ensure that clinical supervision is perceived as valuable for professional growth. These findings highlight the importance of considering individual profiles in refining clinical supervision processes. Teachers in different positions can support each other, with Teacher I and Teacher II helping each other improve their attitudes towards clinical supervision, which is crucial for career progression (Sangalang, 2019).

Table 5. *Difference in Teachers' Attitude toward Clinical Supervision When Grouped According to Respondents' Profile*

Profile	Attitudes towards Clinical Supervision		F-value	p-value	Remarks
	Mean	SD			
School Assignment					
Small (n=28)	3.76	.39	.886	.415	Not significant
Medium (n=70)	3.65	.44			
Big (n=43)	3.63	.43			
Educational Attainment					
Bachelor degree (n=52)	3.64	.46	.760	.519	Not significant
Master unit (n=69)	3.71	.39			
Master degree (n=15)	3.62	.49			
Doctoral unit (n=5)	3.46	.52			
Years in Service					
0-5 (n=36)	3.79	.36	1.487	.209	Not significant
6-10 (n=43)	3.70	.44			
11-15 (n=28)	3.58	.49			
16-20 (n=14)	3.61	.40			
21-above (n=20)	3.55	.44			
Position					
Teacher I (n=81)	3.75 ^b	.40	4.319*	.015	Significant
Teacher II (n=27)	3.65 ^{ab}	.43			
Teacher III (n=33)	3.49 ^a	.47			

Note: Analysis is based on One-way ANOVA *significant ($p < .05$)
 ab-based on Duncan test (same letter means not statistically different)

Difference in Teachers' Teaching Performance According to Profile

Table 6 provides an analysis of the differences in teachers' performance ratings based on their profiles, with F-values and p-values obtained from the One-way ANOVA test.

Table 6. *Difference in Teachers' Performance When Grouped According to Respondents' Profile*

Profile	Teachers' Performance Rating		F-value	p-value	Remarks
	Mean	SD			
School Assignment					
Small (n=28)	4.58	.35	.666	.515	Not significant
Medium (n=70)	4.59	.41			
Big (n=43)	4.67	.40			
Educational Attainment					
Bachelor degree (n=52)	4.53	.38	2.433	.068	Not significant
Master unit (n=69)	4.66	.38			
Master degree (n=15)	4.77	.33			
Doctoral unit (n=5)	4.38	.65			
Years in Service					
0-5 (n=36)	4.68	.34	1.770	.138	Not significant
6-10 (n=43)	4.67	.36			
11-15 (n=28)	4.60	.45			
16-20 (n=14)	4.58	.41			
21-above (n=20)	4.42	.44			
Position					
Teacher I (n=81)	4.61	.38	1.003	.369	Significant
Teacher II (n=27)	4.54	.40			
Teacher III (n=33)	4.68	.43			

Note: Analysis is based on One-way ANOVA *significant ($p < .05$)

Data revealed no significant difference in teachers' performance ratings based on school assignment ($F=0.666$, $p=0.515$), educational attainment ($F=2.433$, $p=0.068$), years in service ($F=1.770$, $p=0.138$), or teaching position ($F=1.003$, $p=0.369$). This suggested that these factors do not significantly impact performance ratings, indicating that teachers can perform well regardless of these variables. The findings indicated the need to reassess evaluation criteria to ensure they accurately measure teaching effectiveness, emphasizing individual teacher qualities and practices over generalized factors. The consistent provision of technical support during the pre-

conference stage, addressing lesson planning deficiencies, likely contributes to the uniformly high performance, highlighting the importance of preparation and support in facilitating effective teaching across diverse contexts and backgrounds.

Relationship Between Teachers' Attitude Toward Clinical Supervision and Teachers' Teaching Performance

Table 7 presents the results of the Pearson correlation analysis examining the relationship between teachers' attitudes toward clinical supervision and their performance ratings. The correlation coefficient (r) of 0.320 with a p -value of .000 indicated a significant positive relationship between teachers' attitudes and their performance ratings. The correlation was statistically significant at the $p < .001$ level.

Table 7. *Relationship between the Teacher's Attitude towards Clinical Supervision and the Teachers' Teaching Performance*

Variable	Teacher's Performance		Remark
	r -value	p -value	
Teacher's Attitude	0.320***	.000	Significant

Note: Analysis is based on Pearson Correlation ***significant ($p < .001$)

The finding highlighted a significant positive correlation between teachers' attitudes towards clinical supervision and their performance ratings, indicating that those with more positive attitudes tend to receive higher ratings. This underscores the importance of fostering a supportive and constructive supervisory environment to enhance teaching effectiveness and professional growth. Alshehri (2019) emphasizes the crucial role of teachers' positive attitudes in successful supervision implementation, advocating for collaboration between teachers and school heads to achieve common educational goals. Sarkar and Behera (2016) further stress the significance of teachers' attitudes in the teaching profession's competence, while studies by Strieker et al. (2016) and Diez et al. (2020) demonstrate how positive attitudes towards supervision contribute to effective teaching.

Influence of Teachers' Attitude Toward Clinical Supervision on the Level of Implementation of Clinical Supervision

Table 8 presents the results of a simple regression analysis examining the influence of teachers' attitude on the level of implementation of clinical supervision.

Table 8. *Simple Regression Analysis of Testing the Influence of Teacher's Attitudes on the Level of Implementation of Clinical Supervision*

Predictor	Regression Coefficient	S.E.	t -value	p -value	Remarks
Intercept	.893	.205	4.356	<.001	Significant
X: Teacher's Attitudes	.739	.056	13.311***	<.001	Significant
$R^2 = 0.560$ ANOVA for Regression: $F=177.184$, $p=.000$					

Note: ***significant (p -value < .001)

The regression coefficients disclosed that both the intercept and the predictor variable, Teacher's Attitudes, are statistically significant ($p < .001$). The intercept has a value of .893, suggesting a baseline level of implementation when teachers' attitudes are zero. The regression coefficient for Teacher's Attitudes is .739, indicating that for every one-unit increase in teachers' attitudes, the level of implementation of clinical supervision is expected to increase by .739 units. The R-squared value of 0.560 indicates that approximately 56% of the variability in the level of implementation can be explained by teachers' attitudes. The ANOVA for regression further supports the significance of the model, with an F-value of 177.184 and a p -value of .000.

The implications of these regression results suggest a strong and significant relationship between teachers' attitudes and the level of implementation of clinical supervision. The positive regression coefficient indicates that as teachers' attitudes improve, there is a corresponding increase in the level of implementation. The substantial R-squared value signifies that more than half of the variability in implementation can be attributed to teachers' attitudes. This underscores the pivotal role of fostering positive attitudes among teachers to enhance the successful implementation of clinical supervision. Educational institutions should consider targeted strategies to promote positive attitudes, such as professional development, communication, and support programs. Recognizing the influential role of attitudes can contribute to more effective and tailored approaches to implementing and improving clinical supervision practices. The quality and type of experiences that teachers have with their school heads during clinical supervision define the extent to which they are motivated to improve their performance (Ghavifekr et al., 2019).

Influence of Teachers' Attitude Toward Clinical Supervision on the Teachers' Teaching Performance

Table 9 presents the results of a simple regression analysis assessing the influence of teachers' attitudes on their performance ratings. The regression coefficients indicated that both the intercept and the predictor variable, Teacher's Attitudes, are statistically significant ($p < .001$).

The intercept has a value of 3.539, representing the expected performance rating when teachers' attitude toward clinical supervision is zero. The regression coefficient for Teacher's Attitudes is .293, suggesting that for every one-unit increase in teachers' attitude toward clinical supervision the expected performance rating increases by .293 units. The R-squared value of 0.102 indicates that approximately 10.2% of the variability in performance ratings can be explained by teachers' attitude toward clinical supervision. The ANOVA for regression further supports the significance of the model, with an F-value of 15.831 and a p -value of .000.

Table 9. *Simple Regression Analysis of Testing the Influence of Teachers' Attitude towards Clinical Supervision on the Teachers' Performance*

Predictor	Regression Coefficient	S.E.	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Intercept	3.539	.272	13.004	<.001	Significant
X: Teacher's Attitudes	.293	.074	3.979***	<.001	Significant
$R^2 = 0.102$		ANOVA for Regression: $F=15.831, p=.000$			

Note: ***significant (p-value < .001)

The implications of these regression findings suggest a statistically significant but modest relationship between teachers' attitude toward clinical supervision and their performance ratings. The positive regression coefficient signifies that as teachers' attitudes improve, there is a corresponding increase in their expected performance ratings. However, the relatively low R-squared value indicates that a small portion of the variability in performance ratings can be attributed to teachers' attitudes. While statistically significant, other factors not captured in the model contribute to the variability in performance ratings. Educational institutions should recognize the role of attitude toward clinical supervision in influencing performance and consider a holistic approach that includes additional factors affecting teaching effectiveness. Promoting positive attitudes, coupled with targeted professional development and support, may contribute to enhanced teacher performance and overall effectiveness in the classroom.

Teachers' emotional support and classroom management predict students' attitudes and behaviors. Nonetheless, educators who are successful in raising test scores are frequently not as successful in changing the attitudes and actions of their pupils. The aforementioned results provide empirical support for accepted theories on the multifaceted character of education and the necessity of devising tactics to enhance educators' entire skill set (Blazar, & Kraft, 2017).

Teachers' job satisfaction and security, along with oversight from school leaders, can affect productivity. Accessible faculty lounges support educators' well-being. Human resources should prioritize teacher welfare for retention. Future research should explore factors influencing teacher performance. A positive regression coefficient indicates a direct correlation between improved attitudes and higher performance ratings. Larger coefficients suggest a stronger positive correlation (Baluyos et al., 2019).

Challenges and Issues in Clinical Supervision

A. What Teachers Liked Most When School Head/MT conducts CS

1. Feedback and Technical Assistance
2. Recognition and Encouragement
3. Opportunity for Professional Growth
4. Pre- and Post-Observation Engagement
5. Communication and Collaboration

The table above highlights the aspects teachers appreciate most about clinical supervision conducted by their school heads or master teachers. Teachers value the detailed feedback and technical assistance, which help them identify strengths and areas for improvement. Recognition and encouragement boost their morale and motivation. Opportunities for professional growth allow them to enhance their skills and teaching methodologies. Pre- and post-observation engagement fosters reflective practices and meaningful dialogue. Effective communication and collaboration create a supportive environment, enabling open discussions and shared professional development. These elements collectively contribute to a positive and enriching supervision experience.

B. Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Clinical Supervision

1. Resource Constraints
2. Time Constraints
3. Classroom Management
4. Pedagogical Competence
5. Learners Behavior
6. Pressure and Anxiety

The table above outlines several challenges teachers face during clinical supervision. Resource constraints, such as unreliable internet, inadequate facilities, and a lack of educational materials, impede effective teaching and learning. Time constraints during observations often lead to incomplete lessons and ineffective time management. Classroom management is complex, with discipline issues and diverse student needs presenting significant hurdles. Teachers also struggle with pedagogical competence, finding it difficult to cater to varied learning abilities and styles. Managing learner behavior, including attention spans and disruptive actions, further complicates the teaching environment. Additionally, the pressure and anxiety of being observed can negatively impact teachers' performance and

well-being. These challenges underscore the need for better support systems and strategies to enhance the effectiveness of clinical supervision.

Aspects of Clinical Supervision to be Modified

1. Number of Observations

2. Separate Observation Tool for SPED

3. Stretchable Time During Observations

4. Peer Observation

The table above outlines key aspects of clinical supervision that teachers suggest modifying for greater effectiveness. Teachers recommend reducing the number of observations to a quarterly schedule, as the current monthly observations are burdensome. Special education (SPED) and reading teachers advocate for tailored observation tools that address the unique needs of their classes. They also propose extending observation times, especially for sessions involving group work or differentiated instruction, to better manage classroom dynamics. Additionally, teachers support implementing a peer observation system where they can learn from master teachers before being observed themselves, allowing them to gain valuable insights and improve their teaching practices.

Conclusions

The importance of having a good attitude toward clinical supervision is central to the findings. Most teachers had a positive attitude toward this process because they understand how important it is for their professional development. Hence, they are willing to participate in reflective activities by accepting criticism as a source of inspiration for growth. Such candor and adaptability highlighted how clinical supervision has the power to revolutionize education.

This positive attitude is complemented by the clear efficacy with which clinical monitoring was implemented at all stages. The approach exhibited a strong framework supportive of teachers' development, from well-organized pre-observation preparations to fair assessments during observations and prompt, encouraging comments in the post-observation phase. This methodical approach fosters a continual improvement culture in educational institutions in addition to improving instructional practices.

Time and resource limitations stand in the way of realizing its full potential. The complex character of these issues is further highlighted by worries about classroom management, pedagogical competency, and the variety of learner requirements. To tackle them, coordinated actions are required, such as the allocation of sufficient funds, focused support systems, and chances for group problem-solving. Furthermore, the study unveiled variations in attitudes towards clinical supervision across different teaching positions, highlighting the need for tailored strategies to accommodate diverse perspectives. Such insights underscored the importance of contextualizing interventions to ensure their relevance and efficacy in diverse educational settings.

Therefore, the results highlighted how important it is to improve clinical supervision procedures while leveraging their natural advantages. This means optimizing the observation process, offering tailored assistance for particular situations, like Special Education, and promoting a cooperative and reciprocal learning environment. Clinical supervision can become a pillar of educational excellence, enabling instructors to reach their full potential and enhancing students' educational experiences by providing a supportive atmosphere for professional development. Future studies may focus on the effect of clinical supervision toward learners' academic performance or a qualitative study on the challenges of clinical supervision in the perspective of school heads.

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